

MICROSTRUCTURE AND PROCESS CHARACTERISTICS
OF 3-D BRAIDED PREFORMS

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ABSTRACT

The microstructures of three-dimensional (3-D) 2-step and 4-step braided preforms are investigated in this paper. Based upon model analysis, geometric and process parameters are identified. The yarn jamming condition is derived and then applied to establish maximum yarn orientation angle and yarn volume fraction. In order to take into account all the variations of yarn orientation angle and length in 3-D braided preforms, the macro cell approach is adopted in the analysis. Parametric study has identified the wide range of variability in the maximum yarn volume fraction.

KEYWORDS: Three-dimensional Preform; Braided Preforms; Jamming Condition; Macro Cell; Yarn Volume Fraction.

1. INTRODUCTION

Composite materials based upon three-dimensionally (3-D) integrated textile preforms have received much attention owing to their high mechanical performance [1-3], and the feasibility of near-net-shape forming using resin transfer molding. Textile preforms are fabricated by existing textile manufacturing processes such as weaving, knitting, stitching, and braiding. Among these, the braiding process is of special interest because it can form complex shapes with superior damage tolerance[4-6]. Depending on the number of steps accomplished in one machine cycle, there are 2-step and 4-step braiding processes.

Characterization and modeling work combined with process study have been performed by many researchers. Analytical models have been developed by Yang, Ma, and Chou[7] to predict the elastic properties of 4-step braided composites using a fiber inclination model.

Processing studies on 4-step braided preforms have been performed by Li, Kang, and El Shiekh[8]. They discussed the effect of machine operation condition on yarn orientation, preform dimension and yarn volume fraction. Recently, Du, Popper, and Chou[9] have developed a model of 2-step braiding to relate the process parameters with structural characteristics such as yarn jamming condition, yarn orientation and yarn volume fraction. The analysis was extended to examine the effect of process variables on the elastic properties of composites by Byun, Whitney, Du, and Chou[10].

Since the reinforcing preforms play an important role in achieving desired mechanical performance of composites, the understanding of fabrication process and preform microstructure is imperative for realizing the potential of textile composites. In this paper, microstructures of 2-step and 4-step braided preforms are investigated to establish the relations between the process variables and maximum attainable yarn volume fraction of the preforms. A macro cell approach [10] is the basis of our analysis.

2. BRAIDING PROCESS

The 2-step braided preform consists of axial yarns intertwined by braider yarns. The axial yarns are straight in the forming(machine) direction whereas the braider yarns move diagonally among the axial yarns. By changing the arrangement of axial yarns, almost any preform cross-sectional shape is feasible. The advantages of 2-step braiding include relatively simple motion sequence of braider yarn carriers and the use of large number of axial yarns for efficient reinforcement in the machine direction. In 2-step braided preforms, the inclination angles of braider yarns vary with their locations. This is due to the fact that all the braider yarns are supposed to have the same pitch length along the machine direction.

In the 4-step braiding process, the braider yarns are all intertwined by their relative displacements. The 4-step braided preform are more integrated than 2-step preforms and the yarns are very wavy resulting in less stiff composites. Because all the yarns of a 4-step preform are inclined at certain angle and are under tension along the machine direction during fabrication, dimensional change of the preform occurs when it is removed from the machine. Another disadvantage of 4-step braided preform is yarn damage due to beating-up motion for yarn compaction. On the other hand, compaction in the 2-step process is achieved by proper adjustment of the yarn converging point.

3. 2-STEP BRAIDED PREFORM

3.1. Geometry of Structure The key parameters for the structural geometry of braided preform are orientation angle and segment length of braider yarns. The braider yarn orientation angle is defined as the angle between a braider yarn and an axial yarn.

Figure 1. Cross-section of a 6x4 2-step braided preform.

Figure 1 shows the cross-section of a 6x4 braided preform. The cross-sectional shape of axial and braider yarns are assumed to be circular and rectangular, respectively. The diameter of axial yarn is D and the braider yarn has thickness d and width w . As stated earlier, the inclination angles of braider yarns change with their locations. It is obvious from Fig.1 that the lengths of yarn segments A and B are quite different and also their orientation angles are different because they must be intertwined through the same pitch length. The pitch length is defined as the length of braided preform made in one machine cycle.

There are four different groups of yarn length in the 6x4 preform. When the width of the preform (m) increases, the number of groups of different yarn lengths becomes more than four. Since it is not convenient to take into account all the variations of yarn orientations and lengths, the average quantities are employed in the model analysis. In the $m \times n$ array, the average length of a braider yarn projected onto the x-y plane (L_p) can be found as

$$L_p = \frac{\pi}{2} D + \frac{2(N_a - 1)}{N_b} (D + d) \quad (1)$$

where the number of axial yarns and braider yarns are denoted as $N_a = 2mn - m - n + 1$, and $N_b = m + n$, respectively. The average orientation angle of braider yarns is, then,

$$\alpha = \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{L_p}{h}\right) \quad (2)$$

3.2. Yarn Jamming Condition The braider yarns interlace the straight axial yarns under tension and the preform is jammed when the neighboring braider yarns on the surface of the specimen are touching one another. At this point the braider yarn angle reaches a maximum. The yarn jamming condition is found from the surface pattern of the preform, and it is obtained by setting the pitch length equal to the longitudinal thickness of the braider yarn [9]:

$$\frac{2w}{\sin \alpha} = h \quad (3)$$

Employing the following definitions of geometric and process parameters, $f_d = D/d$, $f_b = w/h$, and $f_p = h/d$, Eqn.(3) can be rewritten as:

$$\left(\frac{1}{f_b}\right)^2 = 4 \left[1 + \frac{(f_p N_b)^2}{[f_p N_b \pi/2 + 2(N_a - 1)(1 + f_d)]^2} \right] \quad (4)$$

3.3. Yarn Volume Fraction In the calculation of yarn volume fraction, the macro cell approach is adopted, which comprises the whole cross-sectional area and unit pitch length of the preform. The maximum area of axial yarns on the preform cross-section is achieved when they are so arranged that the braider yarns interlace at 45° between the axial yarns. Thus, the volume of the macro cell (V_t) is

$$V_t = [\sqrt{2}(m-1)(D+d) + (D+2d)] [\sqrt{2} 2(n-1)(D+d) + (D+2d)] h \quad (5)$$

The volume of axial yarns and braider yarns (V_{ab}) is

$$V_{ab} = h N_a D^2 \pi/4 + w d L \quad (6)$$

where L is actual length of braider yarn and can be obtained from Eqn.(1)

$$L = \frac{1}{\sin \alpha} [N_b D \pi/2 + 2(D+d)(N_a - 1)] \quad (7)$$

The maximum attainable yarn volume fraction can be obtained when the condition of Eqn.(3) is met:

$$V_y = \frac{V_{ab}}{V_t} = \frac{(N_a f_d \pi/4 + N_a - 1)(1 + f_d)}{[\sqrt{2}(m-1)(f_d+1) + (f_d+2)][\sqrt{2}(n-1)(f_d+1) + (f_d+2)]} \quad (8)$$

It can be seen that V_y is a function of one geometric parameter, f_d , and numbers of column and row of axial yarns. The results of model calculation for yarn volume fraction are shown in Fig.2 for the case of $n=6$. The curves show that V_y increases asymptotically with m .

Figure 2. Variation of yarn volume fraction of $m \times n$ 2-step braided preform as function of parameter f_d .

4. 4-STEP BRAIDED PREFORM

4.1. Geometry of Structure Following the paths of yarns within a unit pitch length, the unit cells in the center of preform have four diagonal yarns as proposed in Ref.[7]. However, unit cells on the edges have more than four diagonal yarns. Figure 3 shows the five types of unit cells in the 8×6 specimen. Each shaded area indicates the location of yarns in the same unit cell.

Figure 3. Unit cell configuration for a 8×6 4-step braided preform.

The key geometric parameter in the 4-step braided preform is yarn orientation angle. There are three different orientation angles in the $m \times n$ preform. The angle can be found by defining braider yarn diameter d , and pitch length h . The largest angle (α_1) is

$$\tan \alpha_1 = 2\sqrt{2}d / h \tag{9}$$

Two other orientation angles can be obtained in terms of angle α_1 :

$$\tan \alpha_2 = \sqrt{5/8} \tan \alpha_1 \quad (10)$$

$$\tan \alpha_3 = \sqrt{1/2} \tan \alpha_1 \quad (11)$$

The 4-step braid is usually formed in a compact manner such that it approaches to the jamming condition. Hence, the angle at jamming (α_1) represents the largest yarn angle, and then α_2 and α_3 can be obtained from Eqns.(10) and (11).

4.2. Yarn Jamming Condition The cross-section of 4-step braided preform cut at 45° from the longitudinal direction is shown in Fig.4 as proposed by Li et al. [8]. The reason for cutting along this direction in examining yarn jamming is that it shows the most dense yarn configuration.

Figure 4. Cross-section of 4-step braided preform cut in the hatched plane.

Assume that the preform contracts in the x' direction; at certain orientation angle, all the yarns are touching one another. Since no more movement is possible, the yarns are jammed in the x' direction. The geometric relation for this case is:

$$\begin{aligned} h \tan \alpha_{j1} &= \frac{d}{\cos \alpha_{j1}} (1 + \cos \alpha_{j1} + \sqrt{1 + \cos^2 \alpha_{j1}}) \\ &= 4d \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

The α_{j1} calculated from Eqn.(12) is 41.4° and h_p (h/d) is 4.53.

Figure 5. Change of yarn configurations on jamming.

When the preform contracts in the z' direction, it is jammed at a larger angle than α_{j1} (Fig.5). Under the constraint that the perimeter of the four yarns must be constant ($abcd = a'b'c'd'$) throughout the further yarn jamming, the following geometric relation can be found:

$$\sqrt{7/16} = \frac{\sin\alpha_{j2} \cos\alpha_{j2}}{1 + \cos\alpha_{j2} + \sqrt{1 + \cos^2 \alpha_{j2}}} \quad (13)$$

where α_{j2} denotes the yarn angle in the z' -direction jamming. The calculated α_{j2} and h_p values are around 60° and 3, respectively. Therefore, at yarn orientation angle 60° , the preform is further jammed and the most compact structure can be achieved.

4.3. Yarn Volume Fraction Since there are different configurations of the unit cells in the preform and also different yarn architecture in a unit cell, it is necessary to take into account all the variations by adopting a macro cell approach. In a macro cell, the different yarn orientations can be identified for the $m \times n$ preform. In order to calculate the average yarn angle, the total angle of yarn segments in each unit cell is computed first.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Unit cell A : } & (2\alpha_1 + 2\alpha_2 + 2\alpha_3) 2 \\ \text{Unit cell B : } & (3\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \alpha_3) (m-4) \\ \text{Unit cell C : } & (2\alpha_1 + 2\alpha_2 + 2\alpha_3) 2 \\ \text{Unit cell D : } & (3\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \alpha_3) (n-4) \\ \text{Unit cell E : } & 4\alpha_1 (mn/4 - m - n + 4) \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Thus the yarn volume fraction is obtained as:

$$V_y = \frac{\pi}{4(m+2)(n+2)} \left(\frac{mn-m-n}{\sin\alpha_1} + \frac{m+n}{\sin\alpha_2} + \frac{m+n}{\sin\alpha_3} \right) \quad (15)$$

The maximum yarn volume fraction can be achieved under the condition of yarn jamming, $\alpha_1 = \alpha_{j2} = 60^\circ$. The values of α_2 and α_3 are obtained from Eqns.(10) and (11). Figure 6

Figure 6. Variation of yarn volume fraction of $m \times n$ 4-step braided preform.

5. CONCLUSION

- (1) The microstructures of 2-step and 4-step braided preforms have been examined to establish their geometric and process parameters.
- (2) The yarn jamming condition has been obtained and applied to calculate the maximum attainable yarn volume fraction of braided preforms. The maximum yarn orientation angle for 4-step preform is 60° and the minimum value of h/d is 3.0.
- (3) The macro cell approach is adopted to predict the maximum yarn volume fraction. It has been shown that the maximum values change with the numbers of column and row yarns in both the 2-step and 4-step braided preforms.

6. REFERENCES

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